

Effects of Ca²⁺ ions on bestrophin-1 surface films

Kirilka Mladenova^a, Svetla D. Petrova^a, Tonya D. Andreeva^b, Veselina Moskova-Doumanova^c, Tanya Topouzova-Hristova^c, Yuri Kalvachev^d, Konstantin Balashev^e, Shomi S. Bhattacharya^f, Christina Chakarova^g, Zdravko Lalchev^a, Jordan A. Doumanov^{a,*}

^a Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Biology, 8 Dragan Tzankov str., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria ^b Institute of Biophysics and Biomedical Engineering, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 21, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria ^c Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Department of Cytology, Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Biology, 8 Dragan Tzankov str., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria ^d Institute of Mineralogy and Crystallography, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 107, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria ^e Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, 1 James Bourchier Blvd., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria ^f Andalusian Center of Molecular Biology and Regenerative Medicine, Centro Andaluz de Biología Molecular y Medicina Regenerativa (CABIMER), Avda. Americo Vespucio s/n, Parque Científico y Tecnológico, Isla de la Cartuja 41092 Sevilla, Spain ^g Institute of Ophthalmology, University College London, 11-43 Bath Street, London EC1 V 9EL, UK

Abstract

Human bestrophin-1 (hBest1) is a transmembrane calcium-activated chloride channel protein – member of the bestrophin family of anion channels, predominantly expressed in the membrane of retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) cells. Mutations in the protein cause ocular diseases, named Bestrophinopathies. Here, we present the first Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) study of the secondary structure elements of hBest1, /A isotherms and hysteresis, Brewster angle microscopy (BAM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) visualization of the aggregation state of protein molecules dispersed as Langmuir and Langmuir-Blodgett -turns and loops (32.2%). AFM images of hBest1 suggest approximate lateral dimensions of 100 × 160 Å and 75Å height. Binding of calcium ions (Ca²⁺) induces conformational changes in the protein secondary structure leading to assembly of protein molecules and changes in molecular and macro-organization of hBest1 in monolayers. These data provide basic information needed in pursuit of molecular mechanisms underlying retinal and other pathologies linked to this protein.

1. Introduction

Best1 is a multifunctional protein containing 585 amino acids and acting mainly in RPE cells [1,2]. Many physiological roles have been attributed to hBest1 – Ca²⁺-activated chloride channel [3,4], regulator of voltage-gated Ca²⁺ channels [5–8], a volume regulated Cl⁻ channel [9], HCO₃⁻ channel [10–12], mediation of glutamate release in astrocytes [13,14] and -aminobutyric acid (GABA) in glial cells [15]. Two models have been proposed for the topology of hBest1 in the plasma membrane presenting four transmembrane domains with or without additional domain lying in one of the membrane monolayers and both the N- and C-termini situated in the cytosol [16,17]. Mutations in the protein sequence, which alter the proposed membrane interacting moieties, are directly connected to macular degenerations and other retinopathies [18–23]. It is particularly important to characterize structural aspects and surface activity of human Best1 protein in order to understand its normal function as an anion channel.

Dickson et al. [24] and Yang et al. [25] described the X-ray structures of a bacterial homolog (KpBest) and chicken Best1-Fab (cBest1-Fab) complexes (with permeant anions and Ca²⁺), presenting a pentameric assembly of subunits that forms a five helix transmembrane pore. Nevertheless, the contemporary knowledge for oligomerization

of bestrophins, determination of transmembrane protein stoichiometry as well as the role of Ca^{2+} -dependent activation for the structural and functional switch of these proteins is not completely understood.

In order to throw a light on hBest1 protein structure, properties, surface behavior and aggregation state as well as the effect of Ca^{2+} ions on structural and surface dynamics, we purified successfully human Best1 from stably transfected MDCK II (Madine Darby Canine Kidney) epithelial cells [26] and applied: FTIR spectroscopy for assignment of the type and the contribution of secondary structure elements; AFM visualization of the molecular organization of the protein in Langmuir-Blodgett films; determination and comparison of π/A isotherms, hysteresis (by monolayer compression-decompression) and morphology of pure hBest1 Langmuir monolayers (by BAM) under physiologically relevant conditions (150 mM NaCl, pH 7).

2. Materials and methods

All reagents and chemicals were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, Mo, USA) unless otherwise stated.

2.1. Cell cultures

Cell culture of stably transfected with hBest1 MDCK cells, cell lysis and hBest1 purification were done as indicated in [26]. Protein concentration of pure hBest1 was determined by the method of Smith et al. [27].

2.2. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

FTIR spectra were taken on a Bruker Tensor 37 spectrometer using ATR accessory. For each sample, 16 scans were collected at a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} over the wavenumber region $4000\text{--}600\text{cm}^{-1}$. The spectra of purified hBest1 in ddH₂O without/with 0.5M Ca^{2+} (hBest1^{Ca}) were decomposed by means of Gaussian fitting in amide I regions; the correlation factor for each peak was no less than 0.9998. Prior to the decomposition the exact band positions were determined from the second derivative spectra. Curve-fitting procedures were carried out by means of three independent samples for evaluation of the experimental errors. The wavenumber error was estimated to $\pm 1\text{cm}^{-1}$ while that of the relative content of specific secondary structure reaches 10% of the calculated value itself.

2.3. Monolayers experiments

All experiments were carried out at identical experimental conditions using a Langmuir balance (Kibron inc. Finland) with Teflon trough, Wilhelmy dynamometric system, and LangmuirBlodgett (LB) equipment for LB-films deposition. 25 L of 15 M $(\partial\pi/\partial A)_T$ hBest suspension were spread on a subphase containing 150 mM NaCl or 150 mM NaCl + 0.5 M CaCl_2 , providing a sufficiently high initial monomer area of $10,000\text{\AA}^2$. After 30min equilibration, the monolayers were compressed and expanded at a rate of $1330\text{\AA}^2/\text{monomer}\cdot\text{min}$. The surface pressure/monomer area isotherms (π/A) and the compression–expansion hysteresis loops (π/A) were recorded. The surface compressibility modulus was obtained as numerical derivative of π/A isotherms hBest1 and hBest1+0.5M Ca^{2+} (hBest1^{Ca}) monolayers were transferred from the aqueous subphase to round glass coverslips (Carl Roth GmbH) (diameter of 12 mm) at surface pressure 20 mN/m, which was automatically maintained. At least three independent measurements were performed for each experimental condition. All experiments were performed at 25°C.

2.4. Brewster angle microscopy studies

hBest1 films were visualized by Brewster angle microscopy (UltraBAM, Accurion GmbH, Germany), which combines high resolution (lateral resolution down to 2 μm) and real-time imaging to supply an information about the lateral domain organization and the morphology of monolayers.

2.5. Atomic force microscopy studies

AFM imaging was performed with NanoScopeV system (Bruker Inc.) in tapping mode in air, immediately after transfer of the protein monolayer from air/buffer interface to the glass surface. Standard silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) probe tips (Tap300Al-G, Budget Sensors, Innovative solutions Ltd., Bulgaria) were used (tip radius <10 nm). The hBest1-covered glass slides were fixed to the metal pads and scanned with rate 0.3 Hz. The images (512 × 512 pixels) were captured in height, deflection and phase mode and analyzed by NanoScope 6.13R1 software in the following order: first order flattening; determination of the length, width and height of the individual proteins; “deconvolution” of the lateral dimensions. The height of the objects was determined as the difference between the threshold value and the highest point of the protein. It is well established that the lateral dimensions of all imaged objects are broadened caused by the tip geometry which has a finite size close to the size of a protein molecule 5 ÷ 10 nm. This artefact is known as “tip-deconvolution effect” and has to be/can be removed by process called ‘deconvolution’ using the relation: $D = -2R + 2\sqrt{R^2 + d^2} / 4$, where D is the real diameter of the protein molecule, R is the tip radius, and d is the diameter measured by AFM [28].

Fig.1. (A) FTIR spectra of hBest1 (black curve) and hBestCa(discontinuous curve) in the amide I (centered at 1638 cm⁻¹) and II (assigned at 1534 cm⁻¹for hBest1 and 1517 cm⁻¹for hBestCa) regions. Decomposition components (dotted lines) and Gaussian fits (discontinuous gray lines) with correlation factor $R \geq 0.9998$, completely matching the original IRS-spectra (black lines) of (B) hBest1 and (C) hBest1Ca.

Table 1

Amide I decomposition components of hBest1 and hBest1^{Ca} FTIR-spectra: wavenumber position, peak assignment, and relative content in%.

Sample	WN, cm ⁻¹	Assignment	Relative content, %
hBest1	1716	COOH group of sidechain-aspartic and glutamic acids (protonated form)	
	1703	COOH group of sidechain-aspartic and glutamic acids (with two hydrogen bonds)	
	1690	anti-parallel -sheets	2.0
	1671	-turns and loops	32.2
	1652	-helix	16.3
	1637	3 ₁₀ -helix	27.2
	1622	aggregated -sheets	14.7
	1610	short helices	7.6
	1598	Sidechain-tyrosine in deprotonated state	
hBest1 ^{Ca}	1716	COOH group of sidechain-aspartic and glutamic acids (protonated form)	
	1703	COOH group of sidechain-aspartic and glutamic acids (with two hydrogen bonds)	
	1690	anti-parallel -sheets	3.7
	1674	-turns and loops	27.2
	1653	-helix	21.9
	1635	3 ₁₀ -helix	29.8
	1621	aggregated -sheets	9.9
	1610	short helices	7.5
	1598	Sidechain-tyrosine in deprotonated state	

3. Results and discussion

3.1. FTIR spectroscopy of hBest1

Secondary structure elements of pure hBest1 protein were analyzed by FTIR spectroscopy. Fig. 1A illustrates the amide I and II regions in FTIR spectra of pure hBest1 and hBest1 in aqueous solution. Despite similarity of the spectra, certain small but significant differences between the two sample variants can be noticed. Both spectra display four main bands: the amide I centered at 1638 cm^{-1} ; the amide II assigned at 1534 cm^{-1} for hBest1/1517 cm^{-1} for hBestCa; CH₂ bending mode appeared at 1463 cm^{-1} for hBest1/1431 cm^{-1} for hBest1Ca; and C O stretching frequency of carboxylic group (aspartic and glutamic acids) involved in one hydrogen bond at 1746 cm^{-1} [29].

To define qualitatively and quantitatively the individual secondary structure elements, we performed decomposition and subsequent band fitting of the spectrum in the amide I spectral region between 1730 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1A) [30]. The Gaussian fitting yields nine components for both hBest1 and hBestCa (Fig. 1B, C). The central positions of the amide I bands (around 1638 cm^{-1}) are assigned to parallel β -sheets, although the asymmetric shape and the shoulders at ca. 1652 cm^{-1} , 1690 cm^{-1} , 1673 cm^{-1} and 1610 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of α -helices, anti-parallel β -sheets, β -turns and loops, and minor polypeptide fragments. The Amide II band (though not as good for assessing the secondary structure of proteins) is sensitive to discrete structural changes in protein due to ligand binding. The most intense band present in the hBest1 spectrum (Fig. 1B) centered at 1637 cm^{-1} (27.2%) and the less intense one at 1652 cm^{-1} (16.3%) originate from 310-helices and α -helices, respectively. Although the band at 1637 cm^{-1} formally is attributed to β -sheet structure elements, for numerous proteins it was assigned to 310-helix [31–33]. The vibration band at 1639 cm^{-1} (assigned to type III β -sheets) actually corresponds to one turn of 310-helix [34, 35].

The broad band at 1671 cm^{-1} (32.2%) is attributed to β -turns and loops associated with the short, extended chains connecting the helical cylinders in highly helical proteins (hemoglobin, myoglobin, cytochrome c, and ferritin) [36]. Band at 1610 cm^{-1} (7.6%) can be attributed to protein anti-parallel strands, or to minor polypeptide fragments found in the chicken Best1-Fab complexes (e.g. α -helices S1a, S1b, S2e, S2f, and S2g) [24]. The signal at 1622 cm^{-1} is assigned to aggregated β -sheets (14.7%) whereas the weak signal at 1690 cm^{-1} to anti-parallel β -sheets (2.0%). The bands at 1716 and 1703 cm^{-1} (associated with C O stretching vibration of the aspartic and glutamic acids sidechain COOH group) [29] are twice more intense in hBest1Ca spectrum compared to pure hBest1, due to twice more buried aspartic and glutamic residues. For sidechain-tyrosine residues, we found that the intensity of 1598 cm^{-1} band is four times less after Ca²⁺ addition to hBest1 (Fig. 1B and C, Table 1). This spectral region and its intensity are possibly related to Ca²⁺-dependent change of the hBest1 secondary and/or tertiary structure. The secondary structure of hBest1 (Fig. 1B, Table 1) is consisted predominantly of 51.1% helical structural elements, including main and short α -helices (23.9% total), and 310-helices (27.2%). The addition of Ca²⁺ cations induces conformational distortions manifested by an increase of the total content of helical structures up to 59.2%, originating mainly from increase of the content of α -helices (with 5.6%), whereas the increase of 310-helices and short helices is small (Fig. 1C, Table 1). Our results correspond well to the published structural information for KpBest and chicken Best1 (405 amino acids, complexed with Fab) which cross the membrane as α -helices, and their cytoplasmic domains form predominantly helical structures [24, 25]. On the basis of Dickson et al. data [24], we calculated approximately 59% content of α -helical structures for crystallized chicken Best1-Fab complexes in the presence of Ca²⁺. The established effect of Ca²⁺ ions on hBest1 structure is consistent with the quantitative analyses of FTIR spectra of calmodulin and parvalbumin which show an increase in the helical content by approximately 6% for both proteins on addition of Ca²⁺ [37]. The content of β -turns and loops (Table 1) comprises 32.2% (~31% in crystallized chicken Best1 in complex with Fab and Ca²⁺). After addition of 0.5 μM Ca²⁺ to hBest1 solution, the content of β -turns and loops decreases (to 27.2%) in favor of helices. The proportion of aggregated and anti-parallel α -sheets (often referred as disordered regions) is 16.7% in pure hBest1 solution and it slightly decreases to 13.6% on addition of Ca²⁺ ions (~10% in chicken Best1-Fab complexes). FTIR spectra indicated that the protein secondary structure was considerably altered under the treatment with Ca²⁺, manifested by increase of the helical structures in favor of the short connecting chains. Binding of Ca²⁺ drives and stabilizes definite conformational changes.

3.2. Effects of Ca²⁺ ions on π/A isotherms and hysteresis of hBest1 monolayers

We have previously established that after inserting of hBest1 in the aqueous subphase beneath POPC monolayer, protein molecules interact with the head-group region of the lipid film [26]. However the surface activity of pure hBest1 is still unexplored.

As Ca²⁺ ions induce conformational changes of hBest1 (FTIR studies), we investigated their effect on the surface activity and behavior of the protein in monolayers.

In Fig. 2, π/A isotherms of pure hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers are compared. Addition of Ca²⁺ ions do not change the initial spreading surface pressure of hBest1Ca monolayer, compared to hBest1. Both isotherms (hBest1 and hBest1Ca) have identical smooth shape and run almost parallel to each other. Reduction of the mean molecular area during the compression induces gradual increase of the surface pressure, without plateaus or kinks that indicate conformational and/or orientational transitions. Despite the equal value of the initial spreading surface pressure (0.6 mN/m) the whole compression isotherm of hBest1Ca monolayer is shifted to lower surface pressure for each monomer area and lower area/monomer at given π compared to the isotherm of hBest1 monolayer (Fig. 2). BAM images, (presented below) demonstrate different films morphology which supported observed behavior. The value of the limiting monomer area A_0 (the minimum area to which the monolayer can be compressed without collapsing), is determined by extrapolation of the steep high-pressure regions of the isotherms to zero surface pressure, yielding $A_0 = 3700 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$ for hBest1 monolayer and $A_0 = 3360 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$ for hBest1Ca. The only so far crystallographic study on the chicken Best1-Fab complexes have demonstrated that a single cBest1 monomer comprises $70 \times 70 \text{ \AA}$ [24], resulting in cross-sectional area of $3850 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$ (assuming the cross-section is approximated to circle). Thus, the limiting monomer area of hBest1 approaches the value calculated for crystals of cBest1 whereas that of hBest1Ca is considerably lower, presumably due to different conformation of the protein and/or different surface packing.

The compressibility modulus, C_s^{-1} , is presented for hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers as a function of surface pressure (Fig. 2, inset). Three analogous regions can be distinguished in both C_s^{-1}/π curves. In the first region when π rises from 0 to 7 mN/m, C_s^{-1} also increases as a result of reorganization of the protein molecules, Fig. 3.

Compression–expansion hysteresis loops of π/A isotherms of hBest1 (circles) and hBest1Ca (triangles) monolayers at the interface air/150 mM NaCl solution without and with addition of $0.5 \mu\text{M}$ Ca²⁺, respectively. And reaches a maximal value of $C_s^{-1\text{max}} = 10.7 \text{ mN/m}$. The maximal compressibility moduli are retained between 7 and 11 mN/m and slowly decrease to the end of compression. The overlapping of both C_s^{-1}/π curves for hBest1 and hBest1Ca suggest comparable stability and compressibility of monolayers below 11 mN/m and less stable (more compressible) hBest1Ca film at $\pi > 11 \text{ mN/m}$. Compression–expansion hysteresis of the π/A isotherms provide additional information about the molecular interactions, structural rearrangements and stability in monolayers. In Fig. 3, we compare the π/A hysteresis loops of hBest1 and hBest1Ca films. The two cycles exhibit similar features – the decompression branches are shifted to lower molecular areas at given π with respect to the compression ones, suggesting that the films are in different state during compression and expansion. The hysteresis decreases, but does not disappear with increasing the surface pressure. The area difference between compression and decompression, at fixed surface pressure, ΔA , is considerably higher for hBest1 compared to hBest1Ca, being as follows: $\square A_5(\text{hBest1}) = 1800 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomers}$. $\square A_5(\text{hBest1Ca}) = 1370 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$; $\square A_{15}(\text{hBest1}) = 670 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$ vs. $\square A_{15}(\text{hBest1Ca}) = 420 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{monomer}$. In addition, the horizontal compression and decompression branches of hBest1Ca at $\pi \sim 0.6 \text{ mN/m}$ coincide, suggesting reversibility of the monolayer state. In contrast, the value of π at the end of the expansion of hBest1 monolayer is lower than that in the beginning of the compression, demonstrating irreversible changes in the molecular organization and/or orientation. BAM images (presented below) demonstrate that at 20 mN/m collapse processes take place, which are irreversible and destabilize hBest1 monolayer, showing definite difference between hBest1 decompression and compression states. Hysteresis of hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers could be due either to a difference in organization/disorganization of the complexes or to “non-return” decompression of protein 3D aggregates (formed during monolayer collapse) compared to the initial 2D state before compression.

Fig. 2. Surface pressure/mean molecular area /A isotherms of hBest1 (circles) and hBest1^{Ca} (triangles) monolayers on a subphases, containing 150 mM NaCl without or with addition of 0.5 M Ca²⁺, respectively. Inset: compressibility modulus, C_s^{-1} , obtained as numerical derivative of /A isotherms shown for hBest1 and hBest1^{Ca}.

Fig. 3. Compression–expansion hysteresis loops of /A isotherms of hBest1 (circles) and hBest1^{Ca} (triangles) monolayers at the interface air/150 mM NaCl solution without and with addition of 0.5 M Ca²⁺, respectively.

3.3. Morphology of hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers

BAM images of hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers are taken after 30 min equilibration right before the compression (Fig. 4A, B) and at surface pressure of 20 mN/m (Fig. 4C, D), where the transfer of LB-films was carried out. The left-hand side corresponds to the hBest1 monolayer and the right-hand side refers to the hBest1Ca film. At the end of the equilibration (at initial monomer area of 10,000 Å²) both monolayers are compact and cover the whole air/buffer interface. However, the hBest1 film is completely homogeneous, whereas hBest1Ca one is inhomogeneous – the compact gray areas of condensed phase coexist with dark regions of non-reflecting low density gas phase, “voids” (Fig. 4B). Under compression up to 20 mN/m, the monolayers density increases, resulting later in reduction of the partial area of the voids in hBest1Ca monolayer from 10% at 1 mN/m to only 3% at 20 mN/m of the total film area, which coincides with the emergence of brighter spots of homogeneous oval shape, size and brightness in the images of hBest1 monolayers. Since, the reflectivity depends on the monolayer density and thickness, we suppose that these bright features indicate the formation of thicker 3D aggregates (collapse of the monolayer).

BAM does not allow distinguishing between the exact conformations of the protein complexes before and after Ca²⁺-treatment but based on the images and π/A isotherms we could state that hBest1 and hBest1Ca monolayers have different packing density, originating from the change in protein conformation, stronger protein-protein interactions and change in protein macro-organization as a result of Ca²⁺-treatment. Our studies demonstrated that hBest1 Ca²⁺-induced structural dynamics/functional switch could be related to the protein macro-organization.

3.4. AFM studies of hBest1

Here, we indicated that pure hBest1 displays significant surface activity and forms stable Langmuir monolayers at the air/buffer interface, which enables Langmuir-Blodgett transfer of the compact hBest1 films from aqueous (150 mM NaCl, pH 7) to solid support and subsequent visualization by AFM [38,39].

Fig. 5 presents the first AFM visualization of purified hBest1 protein. A barrel-like form of hBest1 has elliptic shape with lateral dimensions after deconvolution $\sim 100 \times 160$ Å (± 20 Å) and height ~ 75 Å (± 10 Å). In the presence of 0.5 μ M Ca²⁺, hBest1 protein molecules could form assembly of aggregates with calculated lateral dimensions of $\sim 200 \times 670$ Å and a height of 220 Å for dimeric structure (Fig. 6) (200×990 Å with a height of 220 Å for the trimeric structures, data not shown). Simultaneous formation of hBest1 + Ca²⁺ oligomeric structures (in the plane of the air/solution interface in Langmuir-Blodgett films) is the only possible aggregation mode in the conditions of the experiment in accordance with the established of Ca²⁺ binding sites in the protein molecule [24]. Oligomerization of hBest1 to form dimeric, tetrameric, or pentameric quaternary organization is still under discussion [3, 40]. In the presence of Ca²⁺ ions, KpBest forms stable pentamer crystals, reported also for the chicken Best1 complexed with Fab monoclonal antibody fragments [24,25].

We visualized purified hBest1 by AFM scanning and found that under physiological relevant environment (buffered saline, pH 7), the size of the protein (Fig. 5), exceeds the value of 70×70 Å and 95 Å height, that was calculated for the chicken Best1 crystals (encompassing 405 amino acids).

Enlarged dimensions of hBest1 in the presence of Ca²⁺ ions indicate the existence of completely new ordered oligomeric structure, due to the induced conformational changes rather than just the simple sum of the individual molecules (Fig. 6, Table 1).

The obtained basic results about the structure of hBest1, its monolayer surface properties and effects of the Ca²⁺ ions on protein surface dynamics, conformation and Oligomerization are important for: understanding of the intimate mechanisms of hBest1 functions transmembrane channel; and the role of common consequences of mutations with potential pathophysiological relevance (incorrect hBest1 folding, e.g.). This is the base for searching of approaches to prevent hBest1 misfolded states and to restore functional activity of these incorrect states in pathophysiological conditions.

Fig. 4. BAM images presenting the morphology of hBest1 (left) and hBest1^{Ca} (right) monolayers at different degrees of compression: (A, B) 1 mN/m– uncompressed films

Fig. 5. Representative tapping mode AFM images of hBest1 LB-films on glass slides transferred at surface pressure 20 mN/m in (A) error mode and (B) 3D mode. (C) Height profile from the dashed line in (A).

Fig. 6. Representative tapping mode AFM images of hBest1^{Ca} LB-films on glass slides transferred at surface pressure 20mN/m in (A) error mode and (B) 3D mode. (C) Height

4. Conclusions

By successful purification of human Best1 from stably transfected MDCK II cells [26] and using FTIR spectroscopy here, we prove the existence of specific secondary structure elements of hBest1 in solution and demonstrate the key role of Ca^{2+} in alteration of the protein conformation and topology, oligomerization and macro-organization as evidenced by γ A isotherms and hysteresis, BAM and AFM images of hBest1 in model surface films. We assume that the ability of Ca^{2+} ions to induce reorganization in the lateral structure of hBest1 monolayers, surface dynamics and different protein packing states (experimentally detected on model system) play an important role for protein intra- and intermolecular interactions with other membrane proteins or lipids under physiological conditions, i.e. reveal hBest1 functional switch associated with ion transport through cell membrane.

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